

A Summary of the Status of the EOS Terra Mission Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) and Attendant Data Product Development After One Year of On-orbit Performance

V.V. Salomonson, B. Guenther, and E. Masuoka
 NASA/Goddard Space Flight Center, Code 900, Greenbelt, MD 20771
 Tel.: 301-614-5631/Fax: 301-614-5808/E-mail: vsalomon@pop900.gsfc.nasa.gov

Abstract: The Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) is well. The signal-to-noise (S/N) performance meets or exceeds specifications, band-to-band registration meets specifications, and geodetic registration of observations is near or at 50 meters (one sigma). Some problems with electronic noise, optical leaks, etc. have been identified and solutions to compensate or eliminate these effects have been successful. All ~40 data products are at “Beta” status.

in a paper by Barnes, et al. [1]. A table summarizing the bands and spatial resolution follows (see Table I).

I. INTRODUCTION

The Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) is a comprehensive multispectral imager covering the spectral range between 0.4 μm and 14.4 μm . It obtains near global coverage using a 2300 km swath on a daily basis in 36 spectral bands at nadir spatial resolutions between 250 m and 1,000 m. MODIS was launched on the Earth Observing System (EOS) AM-1 “Terra” mission from Vandenberg Air Force Base on December 18, 1999. Scene data from MODIS became available to the MODIS Science Team on February 24, 2000. The purpose of this paper is to provide a summary of instrument performance and the status of data processing after one-year of on-orbit MODIS performance.

II. BACKGROUND

MODIS was developed to provide improved observations of land, ocean, and atmosphere features relative to “heritage instruments” such as the NOAA Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer (AVHRR), the Nimbus Coastal Zone Color Scanner (CZCS) and the SeaStar Sea-viewing Wide Field-of-view Sensor (SeaWiFS) instruments. In addition, MODIS provides complementary observations to the Landsat-7 Enhanced Thematic Mapper (ETM+) and the NOAA High Resolution Infrared Radiation Sounder (HIRS). There was considerable effort to include capabilities to do on-orbit characterization and calibration checks of instrument performance. These efforts include providing an on-board blackbody (BB), a solar diffuser (SD), a solar diffuser stability monitor (SDSM), and a spectral radiometric calibration assembly (SRCA) within the MODIS sensor. These devices allow comparisons with pre-launch values of spatial, spectral, and radiometric performance. In addition, observation of deep space and the moon are used to characterize instrument performance. A description of the MODIS and pre-launch values of performance are provided

Table I. MODIS Bands

Primary Use	Band ¹	Bandwidth ²
Land/Cloud/Aerosol	1	620 - 670
Boundaries	2	841 - 876
Land/Cloud/Aerosol	3	459 - 479
Properties	4	545 - 565
	5	1230 - 1250
	6	1628 - 1652
	7	2105 - 2155
Ocean Color/	8	405 - 420
Phytoplankton/	9	438 - 448
Biogeochemistry	10	483 - 493
	11	526 - 536
	12	546 - 556
	13	662 - 672
	14	673 - 683
	15	743 - 753
	16	862 - 877
Atmospheric	17	890 - 920
Water Vapor	18	931 - 941
	19	915 - 965
Primary Use	Band ¹	Bandwidth ²
Surface/Cloud	20	3.660 - 3.840
Temperature	21	3.929 - 3.989
	22	3.929 - 3.989
	23	4.020 - 4.080
Atmospheric	24	4.433 - 4.498
Temperature	25	4.482 - 4.549
Cirrus Clouds	26	1.360 - 1.390
Water Vapor	27	6.535 - 6.895
	28	7.175 - 7.475
Cloud Properties	29	8.400 - 8.700
Ozone	30	9.580 - 9.880
Surface/Cloud	31	10.780 - 11.280
Temperature	32	11.770 - 12.270
Cloud Top	33	13.185 - 13.485
Altitude	34	13.485 - 13.785
	35	13.785 - 14.085
	36	14.085 - 14.385

¹Nadir Spatial Resolution 250 m (Band 1-2)
 500 m (Band 3-7)
 1,000 m (Bands 8-36)

²Bands 1 to 19 are in nm; Bands 20 to 36 are in μm

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Salomonson, et al. [2] reported on the very initial results as in the very first few months of MODIS operation. Overall the instrument has continued to perform well in terms of all major subsystems performing well and useful data being produced. There, however, have been aspects of the data that need correction or improvement and they are listed in Table 1.

Table 2
Listing of Instrument Performance Factors Requiring Improvement In Order To Produce Science Products.

- a. Non-Functioning Detectors
- b. *Incomplete knowledge of sensor response across scan Thermal Emissive Bands (TEB).
- c. Incomplete knowledge of sensor time-dependent response function for reflected solar bands (RSB-1 to 19, plus 26).
- d. Degradation correction not installed. Believed to be ~2% in the blue to zero in the red and SWIR.
- e. *Optical cross-talk from Band 31 into Bands 32 through 36.
- f. Electronic cross-talk amongst Bands 5 to 7, 20 to 26.
- g. *Non-uniform digital count bin-fill factors (bin-width), particularly for Bands 31 to 36.
- h. Non-uniform channel to channel response within a band.
- i. Band 21, a fire band, not yet calibrated.
- j. Band 27 anomalous band width, anomalous gain.
- k. Level 1B data sets produced for data days in Nov. being processed with LUT's corresponding to focal plane bias and electronic sides different than those for which data was collected
- l. Scan-dependent Noise (also called mirror-side correlated noise).
- m. Sub-1000m bands misregistered to 1000m bands in 1000m band files

NOTE: *fixed on the MODIS instrument being flown on the Aqua satellite

In essence all of the factors listed above have been and are being studied and improvements are being incorporated as they occur into the Level 1 product. For further discussion of each of the factors noted in table 1 one can go on the World Wide Web to: <http://mcstweb.gsfc.nasa.gov/product.html>. The doors to the instrument were opened in late February 2000 and the instrument has operated continuously since that time except for a short period in mid-summer 2000 when a formatter problem caused the instrument to shut down. The radiative cooler was also not performing optimally in mid-summer also along with continuing problems particularly with items f and g in Table 1. By November 2000 a more optimized voltage setting was achieved reducing electronic

noise (Table 1, item f) and a switch to the "B-side"/backup electronics was accomplished reducing the effects associated with Table 1/item g by about a factor of 2. From these efforts and others, relatively stable, more acceptable operations for MODIS was achieved and sustained to date.

A. Instrument SNR and NedL Results

In Figs. 1 and 2 updated findings are provided that compare post-launch Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) and noise-equivalent radiance (NedL) estimates versus the pre-launch measurements. The results overall are quite good in that they predominantly exceed specifications. The post-launch estimates for the Reflected Solar Bands (RSB) were obtained by viewing out the MODIS spaceport, obtaining values from deep-space, and also obtaining noise values from Solar Diffuser (SD) [1] observations. The SNR is the ratio of the predetermined typical radiances (Ltyp) [2] to noise value scaled between the dark deep space and bright SD values. Both pre- and post-launch values are compared in Figs. 1 and 2 to the specifications. For each band the circles and diamonds represent the results for each channel in the band; i.e., there are 10 values for Bands 8-36, which have a spatial resolution of 1,000 m. These plots give insight as to the uniformity across the detectors within a band.

MODIS RSB SNR from Pre-launch, Post-Launch and Specification at Ltyp

Fig. 1. Reflective Solar Bands SNR showing specifications, pre-launch, and on-orbit values.

In Fig. 2 the (NEdL) results are obtained by using the on-board BB [1]. In this figure the desirable result is for the NEdL's to be less than the specification and as can be seen this is generally the case for the Terra MODIS.

Fig. 2. NEdT Thermal Emissive Bands (TEB) (showing specifications, pre-launch and on-orbit values).

B. Geolocation Results

The specification of accuracy for geolocation of pixels from MODIS IS 300 meters (2 sigma) and the goal is 100 meters (2 sigma). The geolocation goal is driven by the need of the land community for land cover change or transformation studies to be able to have knowledge of pixel location to within one pixel accuracy. As of the beginning of 2001 the goals for geolocation have largely been attained. Products are still being examined to look for problem areas, but to-date the results look quite positive.

IV. MODIS PRODUCTS STATUS

Over 40 science products are being produced from MODIS data. Beginning in the late Fall of 2000 the data processing of MODIS data became relatively stable and since then has been providing complete days (288 granules) of MODIS data up to the present time. The science products are largely in "beta status" and a majority of products are expected to go to "provisional status" by mid-2001. Descriptions of the data products along with their availability are provided at: <http://ftpwww.gsfc.nasa.gov/MODIS/MODIS.html>.

Beginning in June of 2001 there are plans to produce a one-year data set extending from November 2000 to November 2001 that is consistently processed and uses the most up-to-date algorithms. Beyond that reprocessing of data will be dependent on the existence of updated algorithms and the availability of computing resources.

V. MODIS DATA PRODUCTION STATUS

In general the production of MODIS data is proceeding in a sustained fashion and products are regularly being produced. Early problems with getting Level 0 data have been reduced to where reorders are less than 1 percent. The Goddard Distributed Active Archive Center (DAAC) produces the Level 1 data for MODIS at a 2X rate using Origin 2000

computers. This production of Level 1 data will reach a 3X rate with upgraded equipment by mid-year. The production of Level 2 and above products is being accomplished on the MODIS Adaptive Processing System (MODAPS). The MODAPS production is progressing toward a 2X rate. So far 300GB/day of MODIS data are being sent to the relevant EOS DAAC's. Approximately 150 TB of Terra MODIS data had been archived at the GSFC, NSIDC, and EDC DAAC's by the end of December 2000.

VI. SUMMARY

The MODIS on-orbit performance demonstrates that key system parameters are within the sensor specification and are consistent with pre-launch values. Work continues to better understand the MODIS and to optimize its on-orbit performance. Scientific products are being produced for land, ocean, and atmosphere studies that look good and ready for examination and use by the scientific community.

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REFERENCES

- [1] W. L. Barnes, T. S. Pagano and V. V. Salomonson, "Prelaunch Characteristics of the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) on EOS-AM1," IEEE Trans. on Geoscience and Remote Sensing, vol. 4, pp. 1088-1100, July 1998.
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